

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine

VOLUME 2

ISSUE 21 APRIL-JUNE ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

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A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume II, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

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“POEM IN ACRONYM TYPE: C R I M I N O L O G Y”

- **C - Causes of Crime:** Investigating why individuals commit crimes (biological, social, psychological, tenets, and genders).
- **R - Reactions to Crime rapidly:** Analyzing how society and the justice system respond, including law enforcement and public perception in a shortest period.
- **I – Investigation through group effort and collaborations:** United in Examining criminal behavior and profiles.
- **M - Methods of reformation and Rehabilitation:** Developing strategies for correctional approach of rehabilitation and reformations.
- **I - Institutionalizing:** Studying the justice system (law enforcement agencies, prosecution, courts, corrections and Community).
- **N - Nature of Law or the navigation of laws:** Analyzing how laws are made and violated, how flexible in this digital era.
- **O - Offender Profiling and Contextualization in approach:** Understanding the criminal mind, in the context of perpetrator, victims and the community.
- **L – Law :** The imposition of law objectively not subjectively.
- **O - Organized Crime Prevention and Crime Control Program:** Studying specific types of crime and how to stop them and controlling the damage if crime existed.
- **G - Governmental Reaction:** Studying the state's response, such as policing and policy.

- **Y - Yielding to in-depth Truth, Justice & Knowledge:** The overall aim of Criminology Students are producing a body of knowledge regarding crime, Pursuit to crystal clear truth and Justice towards humanity and society.

